

STOCHASTIC MODELING AND ANALYSIS OF MARKET SHARE DYNAMICS BETWEEN TWO COMPETING FIRMS: INVARIANT MEASURES AND EMPIRICAL ESTIMATORS

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Abstract- This paper investigates the stochastic dynamics of market competition between two firms using a system of stochastic differential equations. The model incorporates essential economic parameters such as growth rates, interaction coefficients, and stochastic fluctuations, allowing us to capture both deterministic trends and random market behaviors. We provide a rigorous theoretical analysis of the system's properties, including the existence of a unique strong solution and invariant measures. A Lyapunov-based stability analysis is conducted to ensure recurrence and ergodicity. Empirical estimators for invariant measures, variances, and standard deviations are introduced and computed through extensive Monte Carlo simulations under four representative market scenarios: symmetric competition, asymmetric dominance, low volatility influence, and high stochastic volatility. And we have evaluated the convergence of market shares in these four scenarios and used the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) and confidence intervals, and used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to statistically test the differences between these scenarios. These simulations offer insights into long-term market share behavior and the reliability of empirical statistics under uncertainty. Our findings highlight the impact of stochastic effects on competitive dynamics and provide a flexible framework for analyzing real-world market competition under uncertainty.

Keywords: Stochastic Modeling, Competitive Dynamics, Market Competition, Oligopoly, Invariant Measure, Empirical Estimators, Near-Monopoly.

1. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly competitive economic environment, understanding the dynamics of market share development among firms has become crucial. However, traditional models, i.e., deterministic models, do not take into account the random aspect of this dynamic, given that randomness and uncertainty are inherent characteristics of markets and cannot be ignored, to address this limitation, stochastic modeling has emerged as a powerful tool for describing

the unpredictable nature of economic interactions [16]. In particular, stochastic differential equations (SDEs) have been widely used to model competitive behaviors [22][23], consumer dynamics, and marketing strategies [17].

Recent research has highlighted the relevance of incorporating randomness into competition models to reflect phenomena such as sudden changes in consumer preferences, market shocks, and the impact of external factors [18][20]. These stochastic approaches not only allow for more realistic simulations but also provide insights into long-term properties such as the existence of invariant measures, recurrence, and ergodicity [19][21]. Such properties are fundamental for understanding how companies can maintain or lose market dominance over time under the influence of uncertainty.

In this article, we develop and analyze a stochastic model of competition between two firms offering similar products. Using stochastic differential equations, we simulate various market scenarios, exploring cases of symmetric competition, dominance by one company, and environments characterized by different levels of volatility, where we have used the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs), confidence intervals to Statically Analyze the Simulated Market Shares in these Different Competitive Scenarios, where we have found in the dominance scenario that the dominant company is a near-monopoly.

We have used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to statistically test the differences between these scenarios. Through these simulations, we aim to investigate the empirical behavior of key estimators, including the empirical invariant measure, its variance, and its standard deviation, thus providing a richer understanding of competitive dynamics under uncertainty.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Presentation of the Model

The model consists of two equations. The first equation represents the percentage of individuals who purchase the target product from the first company, which we will

denote as C_1 . The second equation represents the percentage of individuals who purchase the product from the second company, denoted as C_2 . We assume that both companies sell the same product.

We will denote the percentage of customers who purchase from company C_1 as X_1 , and the percentage of customers who purchase from company C_2 as X_2 , where we will assume the following basic assumptions:

1. Target group: Total number of individuals N where $N \in \mathbb{N}$ is constant
2. At any given time t , each individual is either a customer of company C_1 , or a customer of company C_2 , or not a customer of both companies.
3. Assume there is an oligopoly in the market.
4. The companies engage in marketing efforts denoted by m_1 and m_2 , respectively.
5. Transitions from one state to another are modeled as a Markov process or a stochastic differential system.

Therefore, we can express the model as follows: We define $Z = 1 - X_1 - X_2$ as the percentage of customers who do not purchase from none of the companies C_1 and C_2 , therefore:

$$\begin{cases} dX_1 = (\alpha_1 m_1 Z - \beta_1 X_1 + \lambda_1 X_2 Z)dt \\ + \sigma_1 X_1 (1 - X_1) dW_1 \\ dX_2 = (\alpha_2 m_2 Z - \beta_2 X_2 + \lambda_2 X_1 Z)dt \\ + \sigma_2 X_2 (1 - X_2) dW_2 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where, α_1, α_2 represent the customer acquisition rate (by company C_1 and C_2 , effect depends on the size of the free population $Z(t)$, β_1, β_2 represent customer loss rate (Models natural attrition e.g., cancellation, dissatisfaction), λ_1, λ_2 represent indirect conversion rate (positive competitive influence, one company attracts clients from the other through potential clients), σ_1, σ_2 represent noise intensity (market uncertainty, models unpredictable effects: viral marketing, crises, etc.) and W_1, W_2 represent Brownian motions, Figure 1 provides a visual representation of how the different elements of the model interact. Table 1 represents the symbol labels for the model.

Table 1. Symbol labels for the model

Symbol	label
X_1	the percentage of individuals who purchase the target product from the first company
X_2	the percentage of individuals who purchase the target product from the second company
m_1, m_2	The companies engage in marketing efforts
α_1, α_2	the customer acquisition rate
β_1, β_2	customer loss rate
λ_1, λ_2	indirect conversion rate
σ_1, σ_2	noise intensity
W_1, W_2	Brownian motions

Figure 1. Structure and interactions of the competitive market model

➤ Lemma

$$\Delta = \{(p, q) \in [0, 1]^2 : p + q \leq 1\} \quad (2)$$

is invariant under the stochastic system (1).

➤ Proof of Lemma:

On the boundaries $X_1 = 0$ or $X_2 = 0$, the diffusion terms vanish due to multiplication by zero. As a result, the stochastic process cannot exit the domain through these boundaries. On the boundary $X_1 + X_2 = 1$, we have $Z = 1 - (X_1 + X_2) = 1 - 1 = 0$. Therefore, the inflow terms involving Z , which represent customer acquisition from the potential market, become zero. This prevents any further increase in $X_1 + X_2$.

Consequently, the trajectories of the system remain within the domain Δ almost surely.

➤ Theorem 1

System (1) admits a unique strong solution for any initial state $(X_{10}, X_{20}) \in \Delta$

➤ Proof of theorem 1:

To prove this theorem, we need the following theorem: Theorem (Existence and Uniqueness of the Strong Solution for an SDE):

Let the stochastic differential equation be of the form: $d\Sigma = A(\Sigma)dt + B(\Sigma)dW$ with initial condition Σ_0 .

If A and B are locally Lipschitz continuous and satisfy a linear growth condition, then there exists a unique strong solution on a given time interval (to prove this theory, in [1] Chapter 5, Theorems 5.2.1 and 5.2.9 “Sufficient Conditions for the Existence and Uniqueness of the Strong

Solution” or [2][3]). The drift functions A_1, A_2 as well as the diffusion functions B_1 and B_2 , are (C^∞) on the domain Δ . Specifically, the functions are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(a,b) &= \alpha_1 m_1(1-a-b) - \beta_1 a + \lambda_1 b(1-a-b) \\ B_1(a,b) &= \sigma_1 a(1-a) \\ A_2(a,b) &= (\alpha_2 m_2(1-a-b) - \beta_2 b + \lambda_2 a(1-a-b)) \\ B_2(a,b) &= \sigma_2 b(1-b) \end{aligned}$$

According to the Lemma above, the coefficients of the drift and diffusion terms are bounded on the domain Δ :

$$\Delta = \{(p,q) \in [0,1]^2 : p+q \leq 1\}$$

We have Δ is compact i.e. closed and bounded in \mathbb{R}^2 , the functions A_1, A_2 and B_1, B_2 are bounded in this region. Since the drift and diffusion coefficients are (C^∞) and bounded on Δ , we can apply the Theorem (Existence and Uniqueness of the Strong Solution for an SDE), this theorem guarantees that there exists a unique strong solution to the system for any initial condition $(X_{1_0}, X_{2_0}) \in \Delta$.

2.2. Equilibrium Points of the Deterministic System

In this section, we will calculate the equilibrium points of the system (1). For this, we will remove the random part in the model, so the model becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dX_1}{dt} = (\alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 X_2)Z - \beta_1 X_1 \\ \frac{dX_2}{dt} = (\alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 X_1)Z - \beta_2 X_2 \\ Z = 1 - X_1 - X_2 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

We look for equilibrium points $(X_1^*, X_2^*) \in \Delta$ such that:

$$\frac{dX_1}{dt} = \frac{dX_2}{dt} = 0$$

We consider the following cases:

- Case 1: (0,0) is an equilibrium point if the condition $\alpha_1 m_1 = \alpha_2 m_2$ is satisfied (4)

- Case 2: (1,0) is an equilibrium point if $\beta_1 = 0$ is satisfied (5)

- Case 3: (0,1) is an equilibrium point if $\beta_2 = 0$ is satisfied (6)

- Case 4: General Equilibrium (X_1^*, X_2^*)
In the general case, we assume the existence of an equilibrium point (X_1^*, X_2^*) that may not be clearly known, and in order to approximate it we will use Newton's method where we will solve the following system:

$$\begin{cases} A_1(a,b) = (1-a-b)(\alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 b) - \beta_1 a = 0 \\ A_2(a,b) = (1-a-b)(\alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 a) - \beta_2 b = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Let (a^k, b^k) be the k -th iteration of the approximation. Then, Newton's method updates the estimate as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a^{k+1} \\ b^{k+1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a^k \\ b^k \end{pmatrix} - J^{-1}_{(a^k, b^k)} \begin{pmatrix} A_1(a^k, b^k) \\ A_2(a^k, b^k) \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where, J is the Jacobian matrix of the system:

$$J_{(a,b)} = \begin{pmatrix} -(\alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 b) - \beta_1 & -(\alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 b) + \lambda_1(1-a-b) \\ -(\alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 a) + \lambda_2(1-a-b) & -(\alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 b) - \beta_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

2.3. Stochastic Stability and Convergence in Distribution

In this section we will study the stochastic stability of the model and for this we introduce the following Lyapunov function:

$$V(a,b) = a^2 + b^2 \quad (10)$$

It is a C^2 function, radial, coercive, and positive, defined on Δ , where the Ito diffusion operator applied to V gives:

$$\begin{aligned} LV(X_1, X_2) &= \frac{dV}{dX_1} A_1 + \frac{dV}{dX_2} A_2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial X_1^2} B_1^2 + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial X_2^2} B_2^2 \right) \\ &= 2X_1((1-X_1-X_2)(\alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 X_2) - \beta_1 X_1) + \\ &+ 2X_2((1-X_1-X_2)(\alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 X_1) - \beta_2 X_2) + \\ &+ \sigma_1^2 X_1^2 (1-X_1)^2 + \sigma_2^2 X_2^2 (1-X_2)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

We aim to verify a condition of the following type:

$$LV(X_1, X_2) \leq -\omega V(X_1, X_2) + c \quad (12)$$

where, $\omega > 0$ and $c > 0$ constants.

Condition (12) is regarded as a sufficient condition for the stochastic stability of the system at the equilibrium points under consideration ([4], [5], [6]). To do so, we observe the following: the terms $-2\beta_1 X_1^2$ and $-2\beta_2 X_2^2$ ensure a dissipative effect, the positive terms are bounded since $X_1, X_2, (1-X_1-X_2) \in [0,1]$.

Thus, a sufficient condition is:

$$\begin{cases} \beta_1 > \alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 \\ \beta_2 > \alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

So, that the drift term in LV is dominated by a quadratic dissipation. Hence, there are constants $\omega > 0$ and $c > 0$ such that:

$$LV(X_1, X_2) \leq -\omega(X_1^2 + X_2^2) + c$$

For further clarification of Condition (13), refer to the Lyapunov criterion for stochastic stability [4, 5]. In this part, we develop a theoretical framework for the existence of a stationary distribution in the competition model (1) and provide a proof of its existence. Establishing the existence of such a distribution is crucial for analyzing the long-term probabilities of the processes X_1 and X_2 occupying specific regions of Δ .

➤ Theorem 2

Let $\varphi_t = (X_1, X_2)_{t \geq 0}$ be the stochastic solution of the system (1) with:

$$(X_{1_0}, X_{2_0}) \in \Delta$$

Assume that:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_1, \lambda_1, \sigma_1, \beta_1 > 0 \\ \alpha_2, \lambda_2, \sigma_2, \beta_2 > 0 \end{cases}, m_1, m_2 > 0 \tag{14}$$

And the Condition (13) is satisfied, then, the process ϕ_t admits at least one invariant measure π on the domain Δ . This means that there is a probability measure π on Δ such that we take any measurable set $\aleph \subset \Delta$ and for all $t \geq t_0$, we have:

$$\int_{\Delta} p_{(x,y)} \{ (X_1, X_2) \in \aleph \} \pi(dxdy) = \pi(\aleph) \tag{15}$$

where, $p_{(x,y)}$ the probability is conditioned on the fact that the process starts at $(x, y), (X_1, X_2) \in \aleph$ this means that the state of the system at time t lies within the measurable set $\aleph \subset \Delta$, and π denotes a probability measure on the state space Δ .

➤ Proof of theorem 2:

$$\begin{cases} \beta_1 > \alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 \\ \beta_2 > \alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 \end{cases}, \begin{cases} \alpha_1, \lambda_1, \sigma_1, \beta_1 > 0 \\ \alpha_2, \lambda_2, \sigma_2, \beta_2 > 0 \end{cases}, m_1, m_2 > 0$$

Therefore, based on the previous section, Condition (12) is satisfied, meaning that there exists a Lyapunov function such that $LV(X_1, X_2) \leq -\omega(X_1^2 + X_2^2) + c$ where $\omega > 0$ and $c > 0$.

The drift and diffusion functions are (C^∞) and bounded on the domain Δ (the proof of theorem 1), implying that the process is a Feller process [7], [8]. And due to the stochastic perturbation (non-degenerate Brownian motions over all $(X_1, X_2) \in \text{int}(\Delta)$), every interior neighborhood is accessible with positive probability. This guarantees that the process is recurrent or weakly irreducible (For further details on recurrence and weak irreducibility, refer to Chapters 4 to 6 [9]). According to the Khasminskii theorem [5], under the conditions outlined above, there exists an invariant measure π for the process (X_1, X_2) on Δ .

2.4. Empirical Study of the Invariant Measure

In this section, we will define an estimator for the invariant measure. $\phi_t = (X_1, X_2)_{t \geq 0}$ is a solution of the stochastic system (1) on $\Gamma = [0, T]$ where $T \in \mathbb{R}_+^*$, and let $A \subset \Delta$ be a measurable set and 1_A is an Indicator function of set A . We define the empirical estimator of $\pi(A)$ as:

$$\hat{\theta}_T(A) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{\Gamma} 1_A dt \tag{16}$$

where,

$$1_A = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \xi_t \in A \\ 0 & \text{if } \xi_t \notin A \end{cases}$$

Below, we state a theorem showing that $\hat{\theta}_T(A)$ converges almost surely to $\pi(A)$ as $T \rightarrow \infty$, to do so, we first introduce some necessary definitions. We will put forward below a theorem that proves that $\hat{\theta}_T$ converges

almost surely to $\pi(A)$ as $T \rightarrow \infty$ and for this reason we will first list some definitions:

➤ Definition (Positive Recurrence)

A stochastic process ϕ_t is said to be positively recurrent if there exists a compact set $K \subset \Delta$ such that the expected return time to K is finite, and the process admits an invariant probability measure π satisfying $\pi(K) \geq 0$. This implies that the process tends to return to certain regions of the state space in finite expected time (Chapter 9 of [10] or Chapter 4 of [5])

➤ Definition (Ergodicity)

We say that a Markov process (X_t, Y_t) is ergodic if it is positively recursive and irreducible, and the distribution of the process converges to a single constant metric π , regardless of the initial condition. As a result, for any integrable function F , and for almost all paths, the time mean converges to the space mean: Almost surely

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T F(X_t, Y_t) dt = \int_{\Delta} F(x, y) \pi(dxdy) \tag{17}$$

➤ Theorem 3 (Convergence of the empirical invariant measure)

Let $\phi_t = (X_1, X_2)_{t \geq 0}$ be the solution of the stochastic system (1) with $Z = 1 - X_1 - X_2$, under the conditions:

$$\begin{cases} \beta_1 > \alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 \\ \beta_2 > \alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 \end{cases} \text{ and } \alpha_i, \beta_i, \lambda_i, \sigma_i > 0 \text{ for } i=1,2$$

Then, the process $(X_1(t), X_2(t))$ admits a unique invariant probability measure π on Δ , and for any measurable set $A \subset \Delta$, the empirical invariant measure

$$\hat{\theta}_T(A) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{\Gamma} 1_A dt .$$

Converges almost surely to $\pi(A)$ as $T \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\theta}_T(A) = \pi(A)$$

➤ Proof of theorem 3:

$$\begin{cases} \beta_1 > \alpha_1 m_1 + \lambda_1 \\ \beta_2 > \alpha_2 m_2 + \lambda_2 \end{cases} \text{ and } \alpha_i, \beta_i, \lambda_i, \sigma_i > 0 \text{ for } i=1,2$$

In part, 2.3. Stochastic stability and convergence in distribution, we proved that there exists a Lyapunov function $V(X_1, X_2) = X_1^2 + X_2^2$ that satisfies the condition:

$$LV(X_1, X_2) \leq -\omega(X_1^2 + X_2^2) + c, \omega, c > 0.$$

According to the Foster-Lyapunov theorem [9]. This implies that that proves the existence of an Invariant Measure, the stochastic process (X_1, X_2) is positively recurrent and ergodic hence:

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\theta}_T(A) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T 1_A(X_1(t), X_2(t)) dt = \pi(A)$$

2.5. Empirical Estimator of the Variance and Standard Deviation of $\hat{\theta}_T$

In this section, we calculate the empirical variance and standard deviation of $\hat{\theta}_T$. Let $A \subset \Delta$ be a measurable set,

and consider M independent trajectories (X_1^i, X_2^i) , for $i \in [1, M]$, for each trajectory, we compute the empirical estimator:

$$\hat{\theta}_T^i(A) = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \psi_A(X_1^i, X_2^i) dt \tag{18}$$

where,

$$\psi_A(X_1^i, X_2^i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (X_1^i, X_2^i) \in A \\ 0 & \text{if } (X_1^i, X_2^i) \notin A \end{cases} \tag{19}$$

Then, the empirical variance estimator of $\hat{\theta}_T$ is given by:

$$\hat{Var}(\hat{\theta}_T(A)) = \frac{1}{M-1} \sum_{i=1}^M (\hat{\theta}_T^i(A) - \theta_T(A))^2 \tag{20}$$

where,

$$\theta_T(A) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \hat{\theta}_T^i(A) \tag{21}$$

Is the empirical mean of the estimators across the M simulations, so the standard deviation (or empirical standard error) is:

$$\varphi(\hat{\theta}_T(A)) = \sqrt{\hat{Var}(\hat{\theta}_T(A))} \tag{22}$$

so,

$$\varphi(\hat{\theta}_T(A)) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M-1} \sum_{i=1}^M (\hat{\theta}_T^i(A) - \theta_T(A))^2}$$

3. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

3.1. Simulations of the Stochastic Model and Empirical Invariant Measure in Different Cases Scenarios

To illustrate the dynamic behavior of the competitive system between two companies, we propose a series of

numerical simulations of the stochastic model (Figure 2). These simulations allow us to explore different scenarios representative of market situations: symmetric competition, dominance of one company over the other, low influence of companies with low volatility, and finally, a situation of high volatility with equally strong competitive forces. Each configuration enables the analysis of the evolution of respective market shares in the presence of uncertainties and stochastic interactions.

Note regarding the tools that we will use in the simulation in this section, we will rely on the Python language to write the codes and we will use the Numpy and Matplotlib libraries, and in order to simulate the model we will use the Euler-Maruyama method. Regarding the model's parameter values, we were inspired by the approach used in [11-15], since the aim of these simulations is to replicate the model's behavior in comparable scenarios. Table 2 gives the parameter values in the four cases.

Table 1. Parameter values in the four cases

Cases	Parameter values
Case 1: Symmetric Moderate Competition	$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 0.5, \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0.1$ $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.05, \sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = 0.2, m_1 = m_2 = 1$
Case 2: Strong competition from firm 1	$\alpha_1 = 0.7, \alpha_2 = 0.1, \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0.1$ $\lambda_1 = 0.1, \lambda_2 = 0.03, \sigma_1 = 0.25, \sigma_2 = 0.15$ $m_1 = m_2 = 1$
Case 3: Weak influence, low noise	$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 0.3, \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0.05$ $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.02, \sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = 0.1, m_1 = m_2 = 1$
Case 4: High volatility, equal strength	$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 0.5, \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0.1$ $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.05, \sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = 0.4, m_1 = m_2 = 1$

Figure 2. Market share of both companies in four different scenarios

We conducted a series of numerical simulations to better understand the dynamic behavior of the stochastic competition model between two companies. We specifically focused on computing and analyzing the empirical estimator (we will denote $\hat{\theta}_T$ by $\hat{\pi}(A)$ its variance, with $A = \{(x, y) \in \Delta \mid x > 0.5, y < 0.5\}$, standard deviation, and mean across different competitive scenarios. By running simulations for each case, we were able to observe how the distribution of market shares evolves over time under the influence of stochastic

fluctuations and interaction terms. The results highlight distinct patterns: in some settings, the estimator $\hat{\pi}(A)$ stabilizes quickly, while in others, higher volatility leads to greater variability in outcomes. The computation of variance and standard deviation helped quantify the uncertainty around these estimates, offering valuable insights into the level of randomness affecting each firm's market performance. Through this approach, we aimed to capture both the average behavior of the system and its dispersion, thus supporting the theoretical findings with empirical evidence, as Figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of the Empirical Estimator $\hat{\pi}_T(A)$

The figure presents the empirical distributions of the estimator $\hat{\pi}(A)$ across four different competitive scenarios. In Case 1, we observe that the empirical estimator is moderately dispersed around a mean of approximately 0.2818, with a variance of 0.0206 and a standard deviation of 0.1436. The distribution is skewed to the right, indicating that although lower values of market share are more probable, higher shares are occasionally observed due to stochastic effects.

In Case 2, the distribution is highly concentrated near 1 (or 100%), with a mean of 0.9335 and very low variance (0.0024), suggesting that one company dominates the market almost entirely. The sharp peak and low dispersion (standard deviation of 0.0489) reflect strong competitive asymmetry in favor of one firm. For Case 3, the mean estimator is around 0.2343 with a relatively higher variance of 0.0331 and a standard deviation of 0.1818. The distribution shows a longer right tail, implying that while most market shares remain low, a wide range of values can still occur, reflecting more variability and weaker market dominance compared to Case 2.

Finally, Case 4 exhibits a nearly symmetric distribution centered around a mean of 0.3687. The variance (0.0276) and standard deviation (0.1660) are intermediate compared to the other cases. This pattern suggests that the two companies are engaged in a balanced competition, with significant fluctuations in market shares due to strong stochastic interactions and competitive forces. Overall, these results illustrate how the structure of competition and the strength of stochastic effects shape the long-term distribution of market shares, with each configuration displaying distinctive characteristics in terms of concentration and variability.

3.2. Statistical Analysis of Simulated Market Shares in Different Competitive Scenarios

To evaluate the convergence of market shares across different stochastic competition scenarios, we analyzed the empirical distribution of final shares using histograms, cumulative distribution functions (CDFs), and confidence intervals. As shown in the Figure 4.

Figure 4. Histograms and Cumulative Distribution Functions (CDFs)

Case 1 (symmetric competition) exhibits a highly skewed distribution, concentrated around low market shares, with an estimated mean of approximately 28.5% and a 95% confidence interval of [0.2761, 0.2953], indicating a structural disadvantage for the company under consideration. In contrast, Case 2 (dominance of company C_1) shows a strong concentration around high values, with a mean of about 70.6% and a confidence interval of [0.6962, 0.7162], reflecting a near-monopoly situation.

Cases 3 and 4, representing balanced uncertainty and high volatility respectively, show broader and less skewed distributions. Case 3 is characterized by a mean of 49.3% ([0.4790, 0.5062]), suggesting a near-theoretical equilibrium, while Case 4, although centered around 49.5% ([0.4833, 0.5067]), displays greater variance visually evident in the histogram and further confirmed by the smoother slope of the CDF.

To statistically test the differences between these scenarios, we used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The comparison between Cases 1 and 4 yields a test statistic of $D = 0.457$ and a near-zero p-value ($p \approx 1.57 \times 10^{-94}$), indicating a highly significant difference between their distributions. These results confirm that the underlying stochastic dynamics generate distinct market behaviors depending on the competition parameters, and that volatility, dominance, or symmetry each exert a structural impact on the long-term distribution of market share.

4. DISCUSSION

These results shed light on concrete economic dynamics associated with competition between two firms operating in an uncertain environment. The case of company C_1 's dominance (Case 2) can be interpreted as the outcome of a structural competitive advantage such as technological innovation, brand reputation, or distribution networks leading to a near-monopoly situation. Such scenarios are not uncommon in markets characterized by strong network effects or increasing returns to scale. Conversely, Case 1, featuring symmetric competition, reveals that even in the absence of strategic advantages, random fluctuations can significantly disadvantage one of the firms, highlighting the crucial role chance can play in the final distribution of market share.

Cases 3 and 4 illustrate more subtle forms of instability. Case 3, with balanced uncertainty, depicts a market where no firm manages to dominate sustainably; this could correspond to rapidly evolving sectors or to regulated markets that promote fairness. Case 4, on the other hand, introduces increased volatility, resulting in highly variable market shares despite an average close to equilibrium. This is typical of markets exposed to frequent external shocks such as regulatory changes, sudden innovations, or economic crises and underscores the need for firms to adopt robust strategies in the face of uncertainty.

In summary, this analysis demonstrates that competitive dynamics are influenced not only by classic economic parameters (such as price, quality, or cost), but also by the structure of risk and randomness. This suggests that stochastic models provide a more nuanced understanding of real-world markets, particularly in explaining why some firms thrive while others despite appearing equivalent fail in the long run.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we developed and analyzed a stochastic differential equation model to investigate the dynamics of market share competition between two companies under uncertainty. By incorporating stochastic noise and nonlinear interactions, the model captures key aspects of real-world market fluctuations, we provide theoretical guarantees regarding the existence of a unique robust solution and prove the existence of invariant metrics through Lyapunov stability analysis.

Through a series of numerical simulations, we explored various competitive scenarios that reflect different market conditions. These simulations allowed us to compute empirical estimators such as the invariant measure, variance, standard deviation, and mean, offering quantitative insight into the long-term behavior of market shares. Our results emphasize the role of stochasticity in shaping competitive dynamics and confirm that under appropriate parameter conditions, the system remains stable and ergodic over time.

In section 3.2 when we analyze the scenario when one company is dominant than the other, we have found out that the dominant company is in near-monopoly which means that the dominant company controls more than 70% of the market share. This work lays a solid foundation for future extensions of the model, such as incorporating more firms, varying market capacities, or even feedback mechanisms based on consumer behavior. The methodology and tools introduced here offer a flexible framework for both theoretical investigations and practical applications in stochastic economic modeling.

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